

ANALYSIS OF FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF GLAMPING TOURISM*Zastavetska L.,**Doctor of Geographical Sciences, Professor
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The article highlights the main principles of the development of glamping tourism in different regions of the world in the modern period. The authors identify the main advantages of this type of tourism and the threats that arise during the formation of tourist flows in protected areas. The authors note that in many countries in Europe and Asia, glamping tourism is developing thanks to the support of state authorities and local governments. In turn, glamping tourism contributes to ensuring the sustainable development of the territories in which it is implemented.

Keywords: glamping, tourism, territory, sustainable development, camping.

Introduction. In modern life, a person faces numerous challenges every day, including stress and the constant influence of the digital environment, which negatively affects the overall state of health [6]. One of the effective ways to overcome such problems is to restore contact with nature, which is confirmed by numerous scientific studies. Interaction with the natural environment and spending time outdoors, accompanied by a caring attitude towards the environment, contribute to improving physical and mental well-being. In the modern tourism industry, these practices are gaining increasing popularity, becoming the main trend. One of the most striking manifestations of this trend approach is the growth of demand for ecological tourism around the world. Rest within protected areas is very popular, where a new type of tourism is being formed, known as glamping. This concept organically combines elements of the camping subculture and modern ecotourism. Glamping, which emerged as a synthesis of the concepts of "glamorous" and "camping", is a high-class format of outdoor recreation, where comfort and luxury are harmoniously combined with communication with the natural environment. This type of tourism meets the growing demand of modern travelers who seek to enjoy nature without giving up convenience and aesthetics.

Main material. The main factor stimulating the development of glamping tourism in Europe is the growing demand for unique adventures and non-standard forms of recreation. Glamping meets the expectations of modern tourists who seek to combine comfort with nature. The glamping industry itself is a combination of enjoyment of natural landscapes and amenities provided by environmentally friendly, but stylized housing. A feature of such recreation is the possibility of combining luxury with the authenticity of nature. The key role in the development of the market is played by the accessibility and variety of locations for glamping in Europe. Countries like France, Italy and the UK have long attracted tourists with their picturesque landscapes. It is here that the number of glamping locations has grown rapidly, including eco-lodges, yurts, tree houses and safari tents. All of them offer different types of accommodation that satisfy a wide range of tourist

preferences - from families with children to luxury travelers and active nature lovers. The variety of options available allows the glamping format to expand into different markets, making it a popular choice among those looking for an alternative to traditional campsites or hotels.

The development of glamping is actively supported by European governments through the adoption of policies that stimulate sustainable tourism. Many countries are aware of the economic potential of this segment and are weakening legislative barriers to the creation of ecological housing, as well as encouraging private investment through tax breaks or subsidies. In addition, ecotourism is becoming a key direction of the overall tourism strategy of the countries of the region. This not only contributes to the conservation of natural resources through a responsible approach to travel, but also stimulates innovations in the field of glamping infrastructure. New projects are being developed in cooperation with private companies, and existing facilities are being modernized, which has a positive impact on market dynamics. After the lifting of travel restrictions due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the popularity of summer holidays among Europeans has grown rapidly. In response, many glamping service providers are introducing new formats to attract consumers in an increasingly competitive environment. For example, Canopy & Stars, a well-known platform for booking unique accommodation options such as treehouses and yurts, recently expanded its offerings to include themed festival tents, responding to the current demands of its audience and their desire for unconventional ways to spend time outdoors. Large operators specializing in camping and nature recreation are also actively adapting their services to provide improved living conditions. They include amenities such as modern bathrooms, comfortable beds, Wi-Fi access, televisions, cooking equipment and even air conditioning. This approach is particularly popular with family travelers and fans of premium services. Safari operators and companies specializing in extreme tourism are increasingly targeting consumers who are ready to invest in premium experiences, inte-

grating high-end accommodation into their travel packages. At the same time, the growing demand for travel that combines comfort with the opportunity to actively spend time in nature has become an important factor contributing to the increasing popularity of camping among millennials. Such dynamics are predicted to have a significant positive impact on the development of the regional market during the forecast period.

In recent years, Japan, South Korea and Thailand have demonstrated significant changes in consumer behavioral guidelines regarding glamping. In particular, in Japan, the glamping market has experienced significant growth, driven by several key factors [3]. These include the growing demand for unique and unforgettable travel experiences, increasing environmental awareness among the population, and favorable government initiatives aimed at popularizing this type of recreation. Surveys show that the interest of Japanese people in outdoor activities is growing significantly and will have a steady trend of expansion in the near future. This growing demand is consistent with broader trends observed in the global tourism industry. Consumers are increasingly looking for personalized and environmentally friendly travel options. Social networks play an important role in popularizing glamping, providing the opportunity to share personal experiences and raise awareness about the benefits of this type of recreation. In addition, attractive offers from tourism platforms, such as discounts and advantageous travel packages, have a significant impact on the development of the industry. This stimulates additional interest among potential consumers and contributes to economic support for the industry. In South Korea, the development of glamping is closely linked to the involvement of local communities and an emphasis on environmental practices. The integration of cultural aspects into the glamping concept and the maximum use of the country's natural landscapes create a unique experience for tourists. South Korea is famous for its diverse natural landscapes — from rugged mountain peaks to pristine coastlines, which are ideal environments for environmentally responsible tourism. Glamping sites in this country not only promote an environmentally friendly connection with nature, but also activate the role of local communities in their development and maintenance. This approach not only provides economic benefits to communities, but also contributes to the long-term environmental sustainability of tourist sites.

Camping and glamping are deeply rooted in Korean cultural traditions, despite modern technological advances. Local communities actively contribute to creating an authentic atmosphere for these types of recreation, preserving the natural harmony of the environment and developing infrastructure to support sustainable tourism. In Gyeonggi Province, for example, glamping sites such as Pine Valley Glamping in Pocheon combine the comfort of a luxury vacation with environmental awareness, allowing guests to enjoy nature without having to use traditional equipment. The active role of the local community is also evident in the way these sites contribute to the development of local culture and economy. By utilizing local resources and engaging local residents, glamping sites have a positive

impact on the economy and social stability of the environment in which they operate. This interaction creates a harmonious exchange: visitors receive an exceptional experience in comfortable conditions, while communities receive economic support and an incentive to preserve cultural heritage. True authenticity in glamping tourism is achieved through respect for cultural traditions and the active participation of communities in tourism initiatives. In Africa in particular, the community tourism model has become an important factor in socio-economic development. It not only strengthens the position of local populations, but also gives travelers authentic experiences through deep cultural exchange. When indigenous people are involved in the creation of tourism products, national heritage is preserved and becomes part of a vibrant experience for guests. This approach ensures sustainable development of regions and creates multifaceted connections between travelers and locals.

Sustainable tourism encompasses not only environmental conservation, but also the protection of socio-cultural heritage and the well-being of local communities. This becomes vital in regions such as South Africa, where it is important to preserve the richness of cultural traditions alongside natural wealth. African glamping sites offer examples of ecotourism in action: they focus on environmental awareness, minimizing environmental impact and supporting local communities. Babanango Game Reserve in KwaZulu-Natal illustrates this concept, providing guests with an immersion in African landscapes with comfortable modern accommodation. All aspects of the reserve's operations are based on the principles of sustainable development and respect for local culture, making it a model of harmonious coexistence between people and nature.

Partnerships with rural cooperatives and small-scale entrepreneurs play a key role in the development of glamping initiatives, creating sustainable livelihoods and strengthening local economies through new employment opportunities and cultural exchange. In the context of the global transformation of the tourism industry towards more sustainable practices, the development of glamping in Africa emphasizes the need to maintain authenticity by respecting cultural heritage and ensuring the long-term well-being of local communities. One of the important elements of glamping in Africa is the creation of culturally enriched experiences for tourists, which is made possible by close cooperation with local communities. For example, Apex Experience is implementing partnerships with landowners in South Africa, forming a network of eco-cabins and tourism services that integrate isolated regions into the growing ecotourism sector. This model of cooperation not only provides additional sources of income for farmers and hotel owners, but also contributes to the introduction of an environmentally responsible approach to tourism.

One of the brightest examples of such initiatives is the Babanango Game Reserve in the Zululand region of KwaZulu-Natal province. This reserve offers a unique combination of personalized accommodation and interaction with wildlife, allowing travelers to immerse themselves more deeply in the majesty of the African landscape. The glamping concept at Babanango Game

Reserve involves providing modern comforts, while emphasizing the preservation and dissemination of local cultural heritage. This approach attracts tourists who value both luxury and authenticity of cultural experiences. Integrating the traditions and needs of local communities into glamping projects not only ensures the preservation of cultural heritage, but also contributes to the creation of meaningful experiences for tourists. The example of initiatives such as Apex Experience or Babanango Game Reserve demonstrates the potential of glamping as a mechanism that can simultaneously ensure economic development and contribute to the preservation of culture on the African continent. At the same time, the development of environmentally friendly glamping in Africa poses a number of unique logistical challenges that require an innovative approach to ensure the sustainability of these projects. For example, a family that previously led a nomadic lifestyle in South Africa was able to adapt to the new realities and organize their own eco-friendly glamping business during the quarantine. Having moved to Scotland, they created Galloway Glamping in the Dumfries region and the Dark Sky Park in Galloway. The project was implemented with the support of the British Business Bank Startup Loan Program and GC Business Finance. On a 7-acre site adjacent to the Galloway Forest Park, four autonomous wooden houses were built, which ensure that light pollution is minimized and guests are maximally immersed in the beauty of the night sky. The popularization of glamping has also highlighted the issue of its environmental impact, which has made sustainable infrastructure the cornerstone of modern glamping projects. The use of environmentally friendly materials and technologies allows for a high level of comfort without harming the natural environment.

The North American glamping market has been growing rapidly over the past decade, driven by the growing popularity of unusual and luxurious outdoor recreation options. The market is expected to reach \$1,725.7 million by 2030 [5]. Social media is playing a key role in this expansion, as numerous travel bloggers and influencers are actively sharing their glamping experiences, which is significantly fueling interest and demand. The increase in the number of large music festivals and concerts, often held several times a month, is also significantly contributing to the development of this market segment. More and more American cities are using such events as a tool to attract tourists and develop local businesses, which is further popularizing glamping as a modern trend among consumers. Travel web platforms offer attractive discounts and exclusive service packages, making such trips accessible to a wider audience. Short-term weekend trips and city trips, popularized by services like Airbnb, are also contributing to the growth of interest in glamping. This trend covers audiences of all ages: from young people looking for adventure to older travelers who value comfort and nature at the same time. At the same time, the industry faces challenges, including the high cost of equipping comfortable locations with modern infrastructure and the dependence of revenues on seasonality. However, the overall outlook for the glamping market remains optimistic. It is expected that demand will

continue to grow in the coming years due to people's desire to receive unique and authentic emotions that harmoniously combine the spirit of adventure with elements of luxury.

Conclusions. Glamping tourism, which has experienced rapid growth in popularity, integrates elements of luxury with an emphasis on environmental responsibility. This concept demonstrates a harmonious combination of comfort and concern for the environment, attracting environmentally conscious travelers who value minimal impact on nature. Sustainable development practices implemented in glamping areas are characterized by considerable diversity: they include both the use of environmentally friendly materials and the implementation of innovative waste management systems. Such strategies provide guests with the opportunity to stay comfortably while preserving the integrity of the natural environment. An important role in maintaining this balance is played by the development of sustainable infrastructure that allows tourists to immerse themselves in the natural environment without the accompanying negative consequences characteristic of traditional construction methods. The growth in the popularity of eco-glamping has contributed to the implementation of large-scale initiatives aimed at protecting the environment and supporting local communities. These include the use of renewable energy sources, adherence to the principles of "Leave No Trace" and measures to preserve natural heritage for future generations. These efforts not only improve the quality of guests' stay by combining luxury and care for nature, but also contribute to the formation of a deeper connection with the environment and increasing environmental awareness among tourists. Sustainable infrastructure development is the cornerstone of environmentally responsible glamping. Numerous facilities use materials and construction technologies with minimal impact on nature, which creates conditions for the harmonious interaction of humans and the natural environment. In particular, the use of recycled materials or interior elements is common practice. Environmental features of design and construction further strengthen this trend. Energy-efficient solutions, including the integration of solar panels and other renewable energy systems, have become an integral part of eco-glamping spaces. Meanwhile, water-saving strategies such as rainwater harvesting systems or low-flow plumbing help to rationalize water use. In addition, effective waste management and recycling programs help to preserve the pristine beauty of glamping sites. Many glamping sites also place a special emphasis on enhancing biodiversity and preserving and restoring natural landscapes to support local ecosystems. These approaches provide a combination of luxury and environmental responsibility in glamping, which allows it to respond to the growing interest in sustainable tourism.

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